

CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

Anuja Nayak ¹, Bimala Rani ², Manjubala Dash ³

¹ Research Scholar, Himalaya University

² Guide, Himalaya University

³ Co-guide, Himalaya University

ABSTRACT:

Non communicable diseases are increasing day by day. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) as abnormalities of kidney structure or function for more than three months (Gregorio T Obrador, Feb20231). Hemodialysis has been proved to be the effective treatment modality. It results in a marked change in the QOL, due to number of modifications and restrictions, which affect patient's psychological and physiological wellbeing. Further treatment required throughout their life time, the restrictions in food and fluid impose lot of stress, affects their Quality of life. Nearly 10% of the populations were affected by CKD and millions of them die each year because they could not afford the treatment (Dr. Justin Jeya Amutha). Nurses can play a crucial role in enhancing quality of life and reducing complications through simple non-expensive nursing interventions like exercises, Diet, life style modification habits and teaching.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease, consequences

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INTRODUCTION:

CKD is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, which are the primary cause of death for all people living with CKD. If CKD is detected early and managed appropriately, the deterioration in kidney function can be slowed or even stopped, and the risk of associated cardiovascular complications can be reduced. CKD is largely preventable, and can be detected early with simple blood and urine tests. Recent research suggests that around 1 in 10 of the population may have CKD, but it is less common in young adults, being present in 1 in 50 people. In those aged over 75 years, CKD is present in 1 out of 2 people. Globally Chronic kidney disease is the 17th leading cause of death. In many countries it is now among the top five causes of death. In India, CKD as the eighth leading cause of death. [1].

India has the largest number of 2 people suffering from diabetes in the world, with a projected figure of 57.2 million cases in 2025. The number of people with hypertension is expected to double from 2000 to 2025. These will make India the reservoir of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD). At present the therapies for CKD and ESRD are very expensive and beyond the reach of more than 90% of the patients in India. In India, the mortality rate due to CKD has been recorded as 19.2 deaths per 1,00,000 populations. [1]

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end stage renal disease (ESRD) are emerging public health problems in developing countries. A survey was conducted to estimate the ESRD incidence among 572029 subjects residing in 36 wards of the Bhopal city. The average, crude and age-adjusted incidence rates were 151 and 232 per million populations, respectively. The mean age was 47 years and 58% of them were males. They also found that the commonest cause of ESRD was Diabetic nephropathy (44%)[25]. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) refers to an irreversible deterioration in renal function which classically develops over a period of years. Initially kidney failure is manifested only as a biochemical abnormality. Eventually, loss of the excretory metabolic and endocrine functions of the kidney leads to the clinical symptoms and signs of renal failure, which are referred to as uraemia. Chronic renal failure is a clinical syndrome caused by various chronic kidney diseases and is characterized by an imbalance of water, electrolytes, and acidolysis. Disease progression may lead to complete loss of renal function and ureamia [2]

Risk Factors

The universal increase in obesity and diabetes has translated into more patients suffering from chronic kidney disease (CKD). In 2017, the number of patients with CKD was estimated at 843.6 million individuals worldwide [26]. As the disease progresses and kidneys lose their ability to function, patients enter another phase known as End Stage Renal Failure (ESRD), where dialysis is necessary. There are two types of dialysis indicated for ESRD therapy, which are hemodialysis (HD) and peritoneal dialysis (PD). According to the WHO, nurses and midwives make up almost 50% of the workforce of health professionals, and due to their close contact with patients and their families, nurses perform interventions focused on the population with NCDs. In these interventions, one of the parameters that is frequently assessed and attempted to improve is health-related quality of life (HRQOL) [3]

Nursing Interventions

Nursing intervention has been progressively identified as being increasingly important to the improvement of patients' compliance with dialysis. Such interventions, including education, training, and behavioural introduction, which help patients gain more knowledge of dialysis and develop healthy life habits, further improve their compliance with this treatment. Dealing with the chronic kidney patient the investigator found a deviation in the normal body functioning, physical activity, psychological and behavioral changes and also deprivation in value and self-perception which diminish their quality of life. Selective nursing intervention like patient education regarding disease condition, management and/or counselling, diet, healthy life style,

exercise for CKD patients with hemodialysis may be helpful in improving their QOL. Hence researcher felt that it is very essential to discover the quality of life of CKD patient who are undergoing hemodialysis at the selected hospital where it has not been studied and explored prior and also to find out the effectiveness of interventional strategies on development of knowledge, practice&QOL among CKD clients who are undergoing HD & find out association of selected demographic variables withQOL of CKD patients.[4,5]

With recent advances in Medicine, the mortality of ESRD has declined, but the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) studies have identified CKD as a new leading cause of death globally . A recent *meta-analysis* showed that the median five-year survival rate for patients starting dialysis was only 45 %. Nonetheless, patients on kidney dialysis are concerned about their quality of life and survival . The patients perceive the dialysis process as a heavy burden that affects their health-related quality of life (HRQoL) . Patients on hemodialysis should visit the hospital or a dialysis center 2–3 times a week for a dialysis session that lasts around 3–4 h, which can be very limiting and affects the social as well as the professional aspects of their lives. Psychiatric disorders are also common among kidney dialysis patients, with depression ranking as the primary disorder [6,7]

Several studies have reported kidney dialysis complications and how they affect all aspects of life . Patients suffer from increased fatigue, sleep disorders, decreased appetite, malnutrition, physical performance deterioration, sexual dysfunction, cognitive difficulties, pain, and depression .

Renal replacement therapies are miracles of medical technology and the ability of these technologies to sustain lives is of unquestioned significance. However, medical effectiveness is increasingly viewed from multiple perspectives that include more than survival rates and clinical outcome. Patients' functional status, well-being and satisfaction, along with treatment costs, also determine the effectiveness of care . Chronic kidney disease has further shown to affect every aspect of a person's life - their physical, mental and social health. It has been documented that the health -related quality of life (HRQOL) in dialysis patients is significantly impaired compared to the general population . Chronic kidney disease is therefore not only a public health issue but also a socioeconomic problem and a source of disability [8].

It has been clearly shown that quality of life (QOL) decreases with the progression of CKD stages and/or the presence of anaemia, malnutrition, or a history of cardiovascular disease . Further reports have shown a decline over time in QOL in dialysis patients. As time passes patients are more burdened by their kidney disease, feeling more frustrated by the time spent dealing with their disease and the way it interferes with their lives. Patient satisfaction has shown to decline over time [9].

According to the World Health Organization , health is defined as a “state of complete physical, psychosocial and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. The WHO (2009) further defines

quality of life (QOL) as “an individual’s perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns” [10]. Health -related quality of life (HRQOL) is further defined by Finkelstein *et al.* (2009) as the extent to which one’s usual or expected physical, social, or emotional well -being (quality of life) is affected by a medical condition and/or its treatment [11].

Quality of life must evolve from a multidimensional framework which includes physiological, psychological and social well-being as well as satisfaction as a central, core concept [12]. Economic and manpower factors dictate a conservative approach to therapy in most instances in India. The majority of those with ESKD perish because of the lack of funds as very few can afford regular maintenance dialysis. Limitations to dialysis include the paucity of dialysis units, restriction of those units to urban areas, and the absence of sufficient government funding or subsidy and health insurance to cover the relatively high costs of dialysis . Hospitals are grossly inadequate to take care of the vast populations who require care[13].

Considering the significant morbidity and very high rate of mortality among patients with ESKD, efforts are made worldwide in the prevention and early detection of CKD. Prevention, early detection and adequate treatment of major risk factors of CKD such as diabetes, hypertension and obesity together constitute an important public health strategy in this regard and it is critically important in India, where these risk factors are highly prevalent. It has been estimated that successful prevention of these risk factors by public health interventions at population level can result in a reduction of up to 40% in the incidence of CKD. Screening of individuals with risk factors to detect and treat CKD early is another important strategy adopted by various countries for delaying of CKD disease progression [62-64]. Alsuwaida et al. conducted a pilot community-based screening program to detect CKD in Saudi Arabia and demonstrated that it is feasible and relatively inexpensive [14.15].

It goes without saying that public knowledge and awareness regarding CKD is an important factor influencing the successful implementation of CKD prevention and screening programs. Higher rate of early identification of individuals with undetected/early CKD or those at risk of developing CKD might be possible among populations with high levels of knowledge and awareness about CKD. Studies conducted in both developed and developing countries have shown that the public understanding of CKD and its risk factors are relatively poor. A recent Australian study found limited knowledge among participants regarding the physiological role of the kidneys, and less than half of the participants correctly identified hypertension as a risk factor. A study conducted during 2010 among the population of Saudi Arabia showed that less than 7.1% of patients with early CKD reported awareness of their CKD status and there was poor awareness regarding CKD symptoms among the study cohort [16]

Conclusion

Hemodialysis is the preferred treatment for chronic renal failure and is effective in improving patient prognoses. However, the prolonged duration of hemodialysis is associated with increased stress and complications in patients during treatment, resulting in a compromised prognosis. Relevant clinical research has shown that effective nursing care during hemodialysis for patients with chronic renal failure could reduce complications and improve patients' quality of life and prognosis. Together with objective health measures, subjective rated HRQOL is important in the treatment evaluation of patients with chronic disease

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